

Assessing the faculty development programs of St. Dominic College of Asia, AY 2015-2016 and 2016-2017

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Abstract

This study is an assessment of the faculty development programs of St. Dominic College of Asia for academic years 2015-2016 and 2016-2017. Using the institutional semantic scale which highlights objectives, topic, speaker/facilitator, program management, and amenities and accommodation, the study utilized the descriptive design of research using universal sampling of faculty members with a retrieval rate of 85%. The results show that in general, the overall impact of seminars is extremely effective with the exception of seminars on Expanded Tertiary Education Equivalency and Accreditation Program (ETEEAP), action research, and problem-based learning that were rated highly effective. Meanwhile, the evaluation also demonstrates that the topics and speakers who facilitated the seminar were extremely effective. However, least effective among the aspects of the faculty development program is in the area of program management. Thus, it has been recommended to expose the faculty to more seminars and training on student-centeredness and research, as well as to plan for the program particularly carefully and intensively on time management and learning materials like handouts used.

Keywords: Faculty development program; evaluation; seminars; student-centeredness.

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Introduction

Quis custodiet ipsos custodes? Who watches the watchmen? Juvenal, that ancient Roman satirist knew what he was talking about – he gave us the question of who would keep the watchmen in check, not only in power, but in standards and skill? Certainly, it must have been a question for the ages, especially in times where military might decide the fate of nations. But in our case, the watchmen are not police, nor the peacekeepers, or the blessed peacemakers. But the keepers of education, the makers of learning, and the providers of enlightenment: teachers. So, who watches the watchmen, and what will make sure that they are still capable of fulfilling their jobs?

Faculty development is the process of training teachers with up-to-date information concerning their fields of study and industries (McLean, 2007). Steinert et al. (2006, 2016) noted that this is instituted to renew or assist faculty in their roles. This, likewise, includes initiatives designed to improve the performance of faculty members in teaching, research, and administration. In the vein of staff development and other programs in which professionals are trained, faculty development programs aim to keep a teacher's competencies valid in a world of constantly-changing axioms. Plainly, teachers play a critical role in the teaching and learning, and they must be prepared for this challenge (McLeod & Steinert, 2009; Steinert, 2020).

From childhood onwards, we depended on teachers to give us all of our knowledge, from knowing basic skills in elementary school, to understanding theories in high school, and finally, using theories in college. Whether they were called teachers or professors, we always knew that they would give us the answers we needed. But knowledge and understanding, as time goes on, becomes obsolete and replaced with new understandings of the world.

Back then, people thought that the Earth was flat. Eventually, it was discovered to be round. Say that a teacher was not told of this new development, until the day he retired as a teacher, he taught his students that the Earth was flat. This resulted to hundreds of students growing up thinking that the Earth was flat until somebody told them otherwise. This is all because a teacher was not given the new, updated information of his age.

"Academic visibility is dependent upon faculty members' interest and expertise; faculty development has a critical role to play in promoting academic excellence and innovation," said Wilkerson and Ibbey (1998) about how faculty development can not only train teachers and professors to become better teachers but engage them into becoming better teachers. According to Sorcinelli (1994), both junior and senior faculty members have much to gain from faculty development. New faculty members in particular have to not only balance responsibilities and teaching roles, but also the norms of their new campus setting. Faculty development helps them to settle into their new roles as educators.

Austin and Sorcinelli (2013) said that faculty development is key to not only preserve an institution's quality of education, but also to support changes in the institution's curriculum as well. In St. Dominic College of Asia, faculty development programs are held annually for all professors in the four schools. The highlight of these faculty development programs is the two-day seminar held before the first semester of the academic year, in which selected professors would give seminars regarding various topics to their fellow educators. These topics would include the latest trends in specific fields such as General Education core subjects and Outcomes-based Education.

The professors would then be equipped with updated knowledge that their students would definitely need. To put into metaphor, the professors would no longer teach that the Earth was flat, but round. To keep it this way, faculty development must be put in the forefront of any educational institution's priorities, lest the institution risk not only a decreased quality in education, but also damaging a student's intellect in the long-term with faulty, outdated knowledge. This is the natural reaction to the fact that changes and advancements to education in the past years have resulted in teachers being required to become not only creative but effective instructors (Leslie et al., 2013).

Hence, this study aims to evaluate the quality and effectiveness of St. Dominic College of Asia's faculty development program, as perceived by its own faculty members. A faulty faculty development program would only serve to create faulty professors. Their training must be kept at a high standard of excellence, and the most effective way to do it is to ask for feedback from the trainees themselves. Being educators in their own right, the faculty participant would know what improvements to apply in order to make the program more efficient and more significant to their overall development.

Moreover, this study aims to answer the following questions: To what extent the faculty of SDCA assess the effectiveness of the faculty development program as to objectives, topics, speakers / facilitators, program management, amenities and accommodation, and the overall impact; which aspects of the faculty development program are evaluated most and least effective and needs to be improved; and what are the pervasive qualitative comments the faculty shared about the program.

Methodology

This study used the descriptive design of research to evaluate and assess the faculty development program of SDCA. Using an institutional semantic differential scale to evaluate the program and institutional activities, with 1 as the lowest and 5 the highest, the researchers gathered evaluation data from the faculty members who attended those seminars and symposia for the faculty development program. The seminars conducted were evaluated as to the overall impact, objectives, topics, speaker / facilitator, program management, and amenities and accommodation. Questionnaires were distributed to the faculty members after each faculty development program. With the retrieval rate of 85%, the data gathered were encoded using Microsoft Excel and Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Then, the results were analyzed and interpreted and eventually reported to the Office of the Vice President for Academics and Research for future reference in decision making, particularly in the area of faculty development.

Results and Discussion

As to the effectiveness of the program

Table 1. Teaching Philosophy, Growth Mindset, Writing Professional Correspondence, Paper and Pencil Test, and Table of Specifications (October 2015)

Item	Aspects	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	Objectives	4.59	Extremely effective
2	Topic	4.65	Extremely effective
3	Speaker / Facilitator	4.59	Extremely effective
4	Program Management	4.47	Extremely effective
5	Amenities and Accommodation	4.51	Extremely effective
6	Overall Impact of the Activity	4.57	Extremely effective

Legend: 1.00-1.79: Not effective; 1.80-2.59: Slightly effective; 2.60-3.39: Moderately effective; 3.40-4.19: Highly effective; 4.20-5.00: Extremely effective

The School of Arts, Sciences, and Education (SASE) spearheaded the faculty development program with significant seminars on teaching philosophy, growth mindset, writing professional correspondence, paper and pencil test, and Table of Specifications that aimed at retooling higher education faculty members for an expected paradigm shift and migration to Outcomes-Based Education (OBE). The series of seminars and symposium was successful considering how the participants evaluated each topic. This series of retooling endeavor yielded an overall effectiveness rating of 4.57, which is interpreted as extremely effective. Usually, faculty development activities appear highly valued by participants, who also report changes in learning and behavior (Steinert, 2005).

Among the five aspects of the program, the topic received the highest rating at 4.65 (extremely effective), which underscored how the topics offered etched their contribution to the faculty members' preparation for the OBE approach of education. On the contrary, program management, although interpreted as extremely effective, still needs to be improved as this received the lowest rating. Among the indicators in this aspect, time management was found to be a problem. There were too many topics covered in this program, thus, budgeting of time showed to be a challenge.

Table 2. ETEEAP Seminar (January 2016)

Item	Aspects	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	Objectives	4.40	Extremely effective
2	Topic	4.43	Extremely effective
3	Speaker / Facilitator	4.55	Extremely effective
4	Program Management	3.83	Highly effective
5	Amenities and Accommodation	4.29	Extremely effective
6	Overall Impact of the Activity	4.05	Highly effective

Legend: 1.00-1.79: Not effective; 1.80-2.59: Slightly effective; 2.60-3.39: Moderately effective; 3.40-4.19: Highly effective; 4.20-5.00: Extremely effective

The Expanded Tertiary Education Equivalency and Accreditation Program (ETEEAP) seminar exposed the faculty members to possible opening of ETEEAP in the college within the context of the K-12 landscape plus the OBE approach of education. The ETEEAP is an educational assessment scheme which recognized knowledge, skills, and prior learning obtained by individuals from non-formal and informal education experiences. By establishing equivalency competence standards and a comprehensive assessment system employing creative assessment methodologies, higher education institutions may administer competency-based evaluation (De Vera, 2021).

The roles and functions of the faculty were highlighted in this seminar. Factors such as articulation and differentiated instruction were given utmost emphasis for realistic expectations. The speaker was rated extremely effective (4.55) among other aspects, with program management receiving the lowest rate of 3.83 (highly effective).

Table 3. Action Research Seminar (July 2016)

Item	Aspects	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	Objectives	4.02	Highly effective
2	Topic	4.08	Highly effective
3	Speaker / Facilitator	4.02	Highly effective
4	Program Management	3.88	Highly effective
5	Amenities and Accommodation	4.02	Highly effective
6	Overall Impact of the Activity	3.76	Highly effective

Legend: 1.00-1.79: Not effective; 1.80-2.59: Slightly effective; 2.60-3.39: Moderately effective; 3.40-4.19: Highly effective; 4.20-5.00: Extremely effective

Research has not been accepted fully in many institutions because of various issues involved in it, and one of those is time allotted in doing research. Therefore, the speaker introduced a type of research that could bridge the chasm produced by this indifference. Although the topic received a high rating of 4.06 (highly effective), it was evaluated at 3.76 (highly effective), with program management placing last at 3.88 (highly effective). Research may not be very appealing, but the faculty members have rated Action Research Seminar to be highly effective, at least. It is surmised that the faculty have realized they could never disregard research as they have been bound to it while in the academe, considering the challenge of the ASEAN integration, which will make the academic world bigger but tougher for teachers who are research-challenged.

Table 4. SPSS Made Easy Part 1 (September 2016)

Item	Aspects	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	Objectives	4.63	Extremely effective
2	Topic	4.80	Extremely effective
3	Speaker / Facilitator	4.75	Extremely effective
4	Program Management	4.50	Extremely effective
5	Amenities and Accommodation	4.72	Extremely effective
6	Overall Impact of the Activity	4.74	Extremely effective

Legend: 1.00-1.79: Not effective; 1.80-2.59: Slightly effective; 2.60-3.39: Moderately effective; 3.40-4.19: Highly effective; 4.20-5.00: Extremely effective

Computer technology is so ubiquitous these days, and research has benefited a lot because of it as various statistical software is made available in the market. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) has been in the market for quite some time now, but some faculty members have not exploited their use in research. This seminar on SPSS' use was not the first time here in SDCA, but this was offered this academic year for the purpose of improving research development and production as statistics has been implicated to be the 'main culprit' of scarcity of research in the institution. True to what was expected, the seminar was found to be extremely effective (4.74), with the topic receiving the highest rating of 4.80. Again, program management was rated at 4.50, which is also interpreted as extremely effective, but among the aspects, the lowest.

Table 5. Problem-Based Learning (September 2016)

Item	Aspects	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	Objectives	4.40	Extremely effective
2	Topic	4.42	Extremely effective
3	Speaker / Facilitator	4.55	Extremely effective
4	Program Management	3.82	Highly effective
5	Amenities and Accommodation	4.29	Extremely effective
6	Overall Impact of the Activity	4.05	Highly effective

Legend: 1.00-1.79: Not effective; 1.80-2.59: Slightly effective; 2.60-3.39: Moderately effective; 3.40-4.19: Highly effective; 4.20-5.00: Extremely effective

The Outcomes-Based Education (OBE) highlights student-centeredness and tangible outcomes from them. Thus, the faculty members need to adapt themselves to this environment to maintain their relevance and efficiency. Problem-based learning is one way of emphasizing student-centeredness. It derives from a theory which suggests that for effective acquisition of knowledge, learners need to be stimulated to restructure information they already know within a realistic context, to gain new knowledge, and to then elaborate on the new information they have learned, for example, by teaching it to peers or by discussing the material in a group setting. It was also termed the informative processing approach to learning (Kilroy, 2004).

PBL was introduced and elaborated to the faculty participants. This was rated highly effective (4.05) with the speaker getting the highest rate of 4.55 (extremely effective). Program management (3.82, highly effective) is still the lowest among the aspects. This approach is quite novel to teachers. In many instances, this approach has met several criticisms particularly in medical schools because of its tendency for teachers to be "underperforming" according to how students look at the entire process, because this approach is in direct opposite to what Filipino students know about teaching in which the teacher is considered the authority and the sole provider of knowledge. The faculty might have also struggled with the underlying principles of PBL, thus the seminar met conservative evaluation, although it is still high.

Table 6. Road to Professional Regulation Commission (PRC) [September 2016]

Item	Aspects	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	Objectives	4.82	Extremely effective
2	Topic	4.84	Extremely effective
3	Speaker / Facilitator	4.83	Extremely effective
4	Program Management	4.74	Extremely effective
5	Amenities and Accommodation	4.71	Extremely effective
6	Overall Impact of the Activity	4.79	Extremely effective

Legend: 1.00-1.79: Not effective; 1.80-2.59: Slightly effective; 2.60-3.39: Moderately effective; 3.40-4.19: Highly effective; 4.20-5.00: Extremely effective

Licensure examination is one of the determinants of how effective instruction is at a particular institution. Despite its limitation in assessing meeting competencies as it focuses mainly on cognitive skills, licensure examination is one of the factors that influence the overall quality of teachers and teaching (Mitchell et al., 2001). The seminar met so much acceptance as it was rated 4.79 (extremely effective) by the participants. The topic itself turned in a high rating of 4.84, the highest, while amenities and accommodation the lowest at 4.71, which can also be interpreted as extremely effective. As a professional institute as its chosen typology under CHED's new typology of schools, SDCA accepts the challenge to do its best in preparing its students for the licensure examinations given by the Professional Regulation Commission (PRC).

Qualitative Comments on the Faculty Development Program

General comments of the participants are very motivating for SDCA to continue what it has been instituting for the faculty members. Commendations about how the topics relate to their teaching emerged as the most common pattern in the evaluation. Encouraging words such as "good job," "keep it up," and "more seminars like this" are pervasive in these evaluation sheets. These are very general, but these are enough for SDCA to move forward and never cease to provide the faculty enhancement and capability training to hone them and extract the best of them for the students and towards fulfillment of SDCA's vision and mission. However, corroborating the results of qualitative evaluation, time management and handouts are considered weaknesses in the context of high to extremely high effective evaluations of faculty members.

Conclusions and Recommendations

This study highlights the following insightful conclusions from the results. The seminars offered were generally evaluated to be extremely effective in almost all areas, with the topics, speakers, and objectives as the most effective aspects of the programs. Program management and amenities and accommodation need to improve, although, they are rated high, as corroborated by the qualitative evaluation of the teacher participants. Research and student-centered approaches like PBL are less appealing to the faculty when compared with other topics.

Based on the conclusions, recommendations were made to enhance faculty development programs. More seminars should be offered such as topics related to K-12 and OBE that are of interest and relevance to the newest Philippine educational landscape. Careful and intensive planning of faculty development programs needs to be adapted, particularly in the area of time monitoring and provision of learning materials for distribution to the participants like handouts and fact sheets. More seminars about student-centered approach of teaching and research should also be offered. The office should invite speakers who are authoritative on the topic and who can facilitate the seminar or training excellently.

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